

Towards canine immunotherapy models: Monoclonal antibodies with redox regulated epitopes targeting TIM3 attenuate Galectin-9 binding

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ABSTRACT

The TIM3 receptor acts as an immune checkpoint protein. Canine cancers exhibit higher pan-cancer penetrance of TIM3 compared to PD1, highlighting the potential of TIM3 as a compelling target in comparative immunoncology. We have used a highly diverse naïve canine scFv phage library to isolate antibodies to canine TIM3. Alternating rounds of biopanning were performed using either Fc or GST tagged canine TIM3 synthesized in mammalian cells. scFv sequences were identified using colony screening and next generation deep sequencing (NGS). The NGS protocol identified lower abundant frequency clones, demonstrating the enhanced depth of repertoire discovery possible using sequence-tag based tracing. Three representative scFv were expressed as mouse-canine chimeric scFv-Fc fusions or as full-length chimeric IgG. These antibodies all bound to the TIM3 receptor using either ELISA or immunoblotting. All the antibodies displayed sensitivity to reducing agents, which indicates the existence of disulfide-stabilized conformational epitopes. Epitope mapping using pepscan libraries suggested that the antibodies recognize a shared structural motif within the IgV domain of TIM3, within β -sheets fixed by disulfide bonds which would form the conformational epitope. Such conformational epitopes might be functional because they overlap with ligand-binding interfaces. Consistent with this, the antibodies attenuated TIM3 binding to Galectin-9. These data affirm that naïve canine scFv antibody libraries can yield self-antigen reactive antibodies to immune blockade receptor antigens. The data also emphasize the value in using native, folded, mammalian expressed receptor antigens to increase the probability of acquiring conformationally sensitive antibodies with potential therapeutic applications in veterinary and human medicine.

1. Introduction

Cancer is in part a genetic disease whereby key driver mutations exert adaptive survival mechanisms in the evolving tumor [1]. Cancer

cell extrinsic factors, most notably certain cells of the immune system, also form both a barrier and/or a stimulus to cancer cell survival [2]. These cells function as immune checkpoints and can maintain self-tolerance, as well as modulate the intensity or duration of immune

Abbreviations: TIM3, T-cell immunoglobulin and mucin-domain containing-3; scFv, single-chain variable fragment; Hc, heavy chain; Lc, light chain; GAL9, Galectin-9; CDR3, complementarity-determining region 3; Fc, Fragment Crystallizable-tail region of an IgG antibody.

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responses to tissue injury [3]. Immune checkpoint effectors can also be exploited by the tumor to suppress immune system functions [4]. The dysregulation of the immune cell checkpoints can lead to immune cell exhaustion, and a local environment favoring tumor growth by altering physiological factors like oxygen levels, pH, and nutrient availability [5].

The adaptive immune cell branch is composed of both B-cells and T-cells. B-cells are antibody producing cells and can neutralize target foreign molecules to which they have been activated [6]. T-cells, by contrast, can for example detect foreign peptide antigens presented by MHC Class I or MHC Class II proteins on the cell surface [7]. The antibody producing cells and the antigen detecting cells form a coordinated response to non-self-proteins and can play physiological roles in cancer suppression *in vivo* [8]. The immune checkpoint receptors of T-cells can be divided into co-stimulatory or co-inhibitory protein effectors [9]. One checkpoint effector, TIM-3 protein (T cell Immunoglobulin and Mucin domain-containing molecule-3), is a transmembrane protein encoded by the *HAVCR2* gene (Hepatitis A Virus Cellular Receptor 2) [10] and functions as a co-inhibitory receptor that regulates immune responses by interacting with specific ligands, such as GAL9 [11].

TIM-3 protein is composed of three structural domains: the N-terminal extracellular Immunoglobulin Variable domain (IgV), a Mucin binding domain, and a C-terminal Cytoplasmic Tail. The IgV domain of TIM-3 is a protein fold that contains a cleft which mediates the recognition and binding to several ligands [10]. The Mucin binding domain might provide structural support and flexibility for ligand interactions in the extracellular matrix. A cytoplasmic C-terminal region contains tyrosine residues surrounded by highly conserved amino acid sequences that mediate TIM-3's role in signal transduction pathways [12]. Ligand interactions with the IgV include molecules such as phosphatidylserine and Galectin-9. Galectin-9 (GAL-9) is a carbohydrate-binding protein that binds to carbohydrate chains within the IgV domain of TIM-3 [11]. Phosphatidylserine is a lipid molecule that is present on apoptotic cells' surface [13,14]. High-Mobility Group Box 1 (HMGB1) is an alarmin protein that interacts with the TIM-3 pathway, disrupting the localization of nucleic acids into endosomes, thus suppressing dendritic cell activation and tumor evasion of the immune system [15]. TIM-3 also interacts with CEACAM1 and recruits SHP-1 and SHP-2 phosphatases, downregulating T-cell responses and contributing to T-cell exhaustion [16].

Studies of autoimmune diseases in murine models suggest that TIM-3 inhibition can exacerbate diseases such as Multiple Sclerosis, Type 1 Diabetes, Crohn's disease, and Rheumatoid Arthritis because TIM-3 is an inhibitory checkpoint molecule [17]. For example, TIM-3 suppresses Th1 responses and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF) and Interferon Gamma (IFN- γ) [18]; after TIM-3 suppression, immune inhibitory signals are attenuated, leading to uncontrolled activation of Th1 cells, which highly induces inflammation and autoimmune damage [18]. TIM-3 has also been associated with several diseases, including chronic viral infections such as HIV-1, HBV, and HCV [12,19]. In allergic and inflammatory syndromes, polymorphisms in the TIM-3 gene are correlated with airway hyper-responsiveness and Th1/Th2 differentiation [17].

TIM-3 also plays a crucial role in tumor immune evasion mechanisms by suppressing anti-tumor immunity [11]. TIM-3 is expressed on Tregs (regulatory T cells), and its interaction with the ligand Galectin-9 (GAL-9) enhances the immunosuppression function, supporting an immune-evasive environment for the tumor [11]. Tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs) also produce TIM-3 and are triggered by tumor-derived signals via TGF- β ; this promotes tumor growth by inhibiting CD8⁺ T-cell activation and secreting immunosuppressive mediators, such as IL-6 [20]. TIM-3 is also expressed in various tumor cells, where it can directly block CD4⁺ T cell responses, thereby promoting tumor cell migration and invasion, which shows its dual function in immune and tumor cells [21]. In cancer tissue, TIM-3 can also exhibit upregulation on tumor-specific CD8⁺ T cells and Tumor-Infiltrating

Lymphocytes (TILs), contributing to T cell exhaustion [22]. A subset of CD4⁺TIM-3⁺ TILs is Foxp3⁺, indicating a role in regulatory T cells (Tregs) within tumors [23]. TIM-3 modulates dendritic cells (DCs), monocytes, and macrophages. In dendritic cells, TIM-3 promotes maturation and antigen cross-presentation but inhibits NF- κ B pathways in the tumour microenvironment thus reducing tumor immunity [22]. TIM-3's effects on macrophages and monocytes vary, influencing cytokine production and immune suppression through Gal-9-TIM-3 interactions and, these interactions emphasize the importance of TIM-3 in establishing an immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment [24].

The TIM3-Gal9 signaling pathway is an immune checkpoint mechanism regulating T-cell responses and immune tolerance, and it depends on the state of TIM-3. In its unbound state, TIM-3 signalling can evolve from its cytoplasmic tail that binds to HLA-B-associated transcript 3 (Bat3), resulting in a cascade including the actions of: lymphocyte-specific protein tyrosine kinase (Lck), the CD3 domain of the T cell Receptor (TCR), Zeta-associated protein 70 (Zap 70), LAT, Phospholipase C gamma 1 (PLC γ 1), and second messengers IP3 and DAG that together trigger cytokine production and T cell proliferation [25]. Upon binding of Gal-9 to TIM-3, the cytoplasmic tail of TIM-3 undergoes phosphorylation of tyrosine residues Y265 and Y272. This attenuates the binding of Bat3/Lck and reduces the overall signalling cascade. These include reductions in T cell proliferation, lowered IL-2, TNF α , and IFN γ production, and enhanced immune evasion by tumor cells [25].

These data overall highlight the complexity of TIM-3 functions in the many murine and human models used to dissect the role of TIM-3 protein in normal and diseased states as well as cell-specific functions. Understanding the physiological function of TIM-3 in cancers would be advanced if a clinically relevant model could be identified that encompasses the immune-tissue ecosystem. Canine cancers are emerging as a robust model for human disease because they are spontaneous in origin, age-dependent, arise in an environment similar to humans in which their immune systems become educated, and often share molecular features with their human equivalents [26]. PD-1 has been a dominant immune checkpoint target in human cancer immunotherapy [27]. Interestingly, in a recent study in a pan-cancer expression datasets, the TIM3-GAL9 regulatory axis is widely expressed in many different canine cancers-more so than the PD1-PDL1 axis [28]. These data suggest that canine cancers might provide a novel and robust model with which to study TIM-3 signalling *in vivo*. This would include the testing of novel TIM3 specific antibodies as future therapeutic tools. To this end, we have started to generate a panel of anti-canine TIM3 antibodies that can be used in the future to model the impacts of TIM3 on the many immune cell interactions it is known to be involved with *in vivo*.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

All chemicals were acquired from Sigma Aldrich unless otherwise indicated. The naïve canine scFv library was previously reported, being used to isolate antibodies to canine PD1 [29]. ER2738, which is a tetracycline resistant F⁺ bacterium, was from New England Biolabs (catalogue number E4104). DH5 α bacterial cells used for plasmid preparation were obtained from Thermo Fisher. The primary HRP-conjugated anti-M13 phage antibody (Santa Cruz, catalogue number sc-53004) was used to measure scFV phage binding using immunoplates. M13 helper phage KO7 was obtained from NEB (catalogue number N0315S). GAL9 protein (*E.coli*-derived human Galectin-9 protein, Ala2-Thr323) was obtained from R&D systems (2025-GA). Product details from the R&D website states that if human GAL9 is immobilized at 1 μ g/mL in an immunoplate well (100 μ L/well), then recombinant Canine TIM-3 Fc Chimera can bind. This same GAL9 assay format was used in Fig. 11 to test the effects of the anti-TIM3 antibodies on the Fc-TIM3-GAL9 interactions. HRP conjugated anti-mouse antibody was from DAKO (P0260).

2.2. TIM3 protein purification from eukaryotic cells

TIM3 fusion proteins were purified using the extracellular domain of canine TIM3 from mammalian cells by the University of Dundee Protein Purification facility. Tim3His (Twist Biosciences), Tim3Fc (Twist Biosciences, 468 amino acid fusion with extracellular TIM3 (237 amino acids TIM3 with human Fc domain), and Tim3GST (MRC PPU Reagents & Services DU61779) plasmid DNA was transfected into Expi293 cells using the Gibco Expi293 Expression System Kit according to the manufacturer's guidelines. The resulting fusion proteins were purified from the expression media via batch affinity chromatography using Ni-NTA, Protein A, or glutathione resins respectively, according to standard protocols. The experimental for the GST construct is: Tim3 was PCR amplified from Tim3His (Twist Biosciences) using DNA oligonucleotides JC826/827 (Merck). The PCR product was double digested using restriction enzymes *Bam*H1 and *Not*I (Thermo Scientific) in the absence of stop solution, inserted into a *Bam*H1 and *Not*I digested vector pCDNA5D FRT/TO C-GST (MRC PPU Reagents & Services DU41665), and ligated with T4 DNA ligase (NEB). The clone was transformed into DH5α cells and the isolated plasmid DNA verified by DNA sequencing.

2.3. scFv phage library biopanning against TIM3 protein

The TIM3 extracellular receptor domain was purified using different tags (Fig. 1). A High Protein Binding microtiter plate (Corning, catalogue number 3922), was coated with either GST or FC tagged TIM3 protein (1 μg) in 100 or 200 μl of sodium carbonate buffer (0.1 M) overnight at 4°C. The wells were blocked with 200 μl of a buffer containing PBS with 0.1 % (v/v) Tween-20 and 3 % BSA for 1 h at room temperature. After washing three times with PBS containing 0.1 % (v/v) Tween-20, the parental phage (~2–20 μl in a 100–200 μl final volume) or subsequent phage pools, were added into a buffer (100 or 200 μl) containing PBS with 0.1 % (v/v) Tween-20 and 3 % BSA to allow the phage to bind to the target, as reported previously [29]. High pH elution was performed by incubating the wells for 15 min at room temperature with 100 or 200 μl of the 0.1 M triethylamine buffer, neutralization using 35 μl or 70 μl of a buffer containing Tris-HCl, pH 7.4 (1 M), and then amplification and propagating the phage by infection of log phase ER2738 cells (1–2 ml) and incubated at room temperature for 15 min. The infected cells were added to 10–20 ml of LB-Amp (100 μg/ml) and incubated at 37°C with shaking for 90 min before the addition of the M13 helper phage (5–10 μl). The cells were incubated with shaking 37°C for 90 min and then kanamycin was added (50 μg/ml) and incubated

overnight at 30°C with shaking. The following day, the phages were precipitated by adding 1/5 volume of 2.5 M NaCl/20 %PEG8000 and each pellet was resuspended in 0.25–0.5 ml of PBS. These four rounds of phage were used for NGS sequencing to measure enrichment efficiency (as in Fig. 3).

2.4. Methodology for measuring CDR3 sequence diversity enrichment during biopanning

Antibody genes were amplified by PCR using primers that were tagged at their C-terminal end with 3 bp bar-codes that allowed extraction from a pool of reaction products (Fig. 2C). This pooling of bar-coded amplicons from different rounds of biopanning allows for NGS to be performed in one sequencing reaction, using the strategy in Fig. 2C. Each PCR amplicon was produced using 44 bp forward primers that contain the original 1st generation Illumina forward adapter (Fig. 2C–(i), 5'-ACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT-3' followed by the pelB sequence 5'ATGAAATACCTATTGCCTACGGCA-3'. The pelB sequence is upstream of FR1 of the antibody gene and is used to direct the scFv for secretion in bacteria. The ~60 bp variable length reverse primer sequences included the 1st generation Illumina reverse adaptor (Fig. 2C), (ii), 5'-GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCT-3', followed by the triplet bar code, and then four different sequences that have part of FR4 (see Fig. 2C sequences listed in green). These FR4 sequences form the C-terminal end of the FR4 heavy chain sequence which is listed in Fig. 2C (iii). The PCR reactions (25 μl volume) used the forward primer (at 1 μM) and the four reverse primers (all pooled at final 1 μM concentrations), 0.2 μl of phage particles (~>10¹¹ pfu/ml), and an equal volume of 2X Pfu DNA polymerase. After 35 cycles (65 °C primer hybridization and 72 °C elongation for 1 min), the amplicons were separated using an agarose gel (1.5 %) in TEA buffer to see if ~ 400–500 bp products were observed (Fig. 2D). The amplicons were excised and purified. The amplicon concentration ranged from 10 to 100 ng/μl in TBE buffer. All amplicons were pooled into one reaction (containing 10 μl of 10 ng/ul of each) for processing by Source Bioscience (Cambridge, UK). The pooled bar-coded amplicons were blunt end ligated using the new generation of Illumina adaptor (NEB Next® Ultra™ II for DNA Library Prep). This new generation of adaptor sequences are Adaptor Read 1 5'-AGATCGGAA-GAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCA-3'. and Adaptor Read 2 5'-AGATCGGAAGAGCGTCGTGTAGGGAAAGAGTGT-3'. From raw sequencing files (containing ~>1–6 M sequencing reads), the indexed DNA sequencing reads that passed quality control were extracted. A programme was previously developed to extract short read DNA

Fig. 1. TIM3 antigens used for biopanning. (A). A sequence comparison of canine TIM3 and human TIM3. (B). The relative purity of the extracellular domains of canine TIM3 when fused to either Fc tag or GST and expressed in a mammalian expression system to maintain its native conformation including disulfide linkages. These two TIM3 receptor domains were used in alternating biopanning screens to select for TIM3 binding scFv from a fully canine-derived naive scFv phage display library [29].

A. scFv phage TIM3 biopanning strategy

- Affinity purify Fc or GST tagged TIM3 from eukaryotic expression systems
- Alternate tagged proteins in each round to minimize acquisition of scFv to tags
- After four rounds of biopanning, quantitate efficiency using NGS
- After four rounds of biopanning, isolate individual scFv using standard colony picking

B. Methodologies used after biopanning

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Direct representation of clone abundance -No PCR required to isolate scFv plasmids -Does not capture rare clones -Low throughput | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Rapidly quantitates efficiency of biopanning -Identifies low-abundance clones -Possible PCR Amplification bias -High throughput |
|--|---|

C. 1st gen-ILLUMINA AMPLICON IS BLUNT END LIGATED WITH the 2nd gen-ILLUMINA PRIMERS

i. One forward PCR primer

FORWARD ILLUMINA ADAPTOR (IN RED) PELB SEQUENCE PRIMER (IN BRONZE)

5'ACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTATGAAATACCTATTGCCTACGGCA-3'
 amino acid sequence M K Y L L P T A

ii. Four Reverse PCR primers with bar code

REVERSE ILLUMINA ADAPTOR 3 bp bar code

5'GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCT AAA TGAGGAGACGGTGACCAGGGT
 5'GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCT AAA TGAGGAGACGGTGACCAGGGTSC
 5'GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCT AAA TGAGGAGACGGTGACCAGGGC
 5'GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCT AAA TGAGGACACGAAGAGTGAGGT

iii. reverse translate FR4 amino acid sequences:

REPRESENTATIVE FR4 SEQUENCE: WGQGLVTV
 TLVTVSS
 ALVTVSS
 TSLFVSS

} EXAMPLES OF DEGENERATE FR4 SEQUENCES

D. Amplification of bar-coded phage

Fig. 2. Measuring biopanning efficiency using PCR based NGS methodologies. A. General strategy for scFv phage library biopanning against TIM3. B. Strengths and limitations of the two methodologies used after biopanning to identify monoclonal antibody sequences. C. Shown are the position and sequence of the 1st generation-Illumina adaptor sequences and (i) the forward primer; (ii) the four reverse primers with the three bp bar codes, and (iii) FR4 translation of the reverse primers. D. The PCR amplicons produced using these primers with phage pools R1-R4 from the TIM3 screening are ~500 bp (lanes 5–8, TIM3 panel). A control protein was used in lanes 1–4, control panel.

A. General structure of the scFv fusion gene

B. Top enriched CDR3 sequences as a function of rounds of screening

name	AGT Parental Counts	TTC ROUND 1	AAT ROUND 2	AAC ROUND 3	AAG ROUND 4	FOLD ENRICHMENT
scFv11	8115	5333	7477	2552516	4509828	555,7
scFv5	1028	584	886	213947	299982	291,8
scFv31	382	308	510	183094	103957	272,1
scFv3	381	200	355	181573	95252	250
scFv22	557	174	322	45205	64384	115,5
scFv13	196	110	155	52590	41370	211
scFv12	231	70	154	32856	14367	62,1
scFv17	86	43	66	18721	7265	84,4

C. Plot of read counts as a function of rounds of screening

Fig. 3. NGS CDR3 reads from biopanning screen. (A). Example image of the scFv gene structure with *pelB* leader sequence and variable domains. (B). Examples of the number of CDR3 sequences enriched in rounds 1–4. The most dominant antibody enriched based on CDR3 sequence reads was highly enriched in rounds 3 and 4 are scFv-11. The data are represented as number of reads as a function of each round and includes the number of reads detected in the parental library (bar coded AGT). The data do not quantify the true abundance of any one given antibody sequence because the amplicons were generated using over 30 cycles of PCR. There can be PCR bias in the amplification however this method can be used to identify clones of low abundance by colony sequencing. (C). Plotting of the data from Fig. 3B to visualize the distribution of clones emerging in rounds 3 and 4.

sequences from scFv genes using next generation sequencing platforms (Illumina). The DNA sequences were then translated to define amino acid sequences in each pool of biopanning. The codes used to extract the heavy chain CDR3 sequences were previously detailed [29], DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14512819. Alignment started after the triplet barcode, with sequences containing FR4 (such as 5'TGAGGAGACGGTGACCAGGGCT-3' (Fig. 2C (ii)).

2.5. ELISA assessment of scFv-phage TIM3 binding activity

The target antigens (Fc-TIM3, GST-TIM3, his-TIM3, Fc-CTLA4, and/or GST-scFv-PD1) were coated overnight (200 ng/well, unless indicated

otherwise) in a 96 well immunoplate plate in 100 μ l of 0.1 M sodium carbonate buffer (pH 9.0). Wells were washed three times with 250 μ l of PBS-Tween-20 (0.1 %, v/v) (PT buffer) and then blocked with PBS-Tween (0.1 %, v/v)-BSA (3 % w/v) (PTB buffer) for 1 h. Blocking buffer was then removed, and 100 μ l of scFv-phage antibody pools or purified monoclonal phage (Fig. 4) diluted in PTB buffer was added to the wells. Following a 1-h incubation, wells were washed four times with PT buffer as above. The anti-M13 phage (mouse) monoclonal antibody was added (1:1000 dilution in PTB buffer) for 1 h, followed by the addition of HRP conjugated anti-mouse HRP (1:1000 dilution in PTB buffer) for 1 h. Wells were washed three times with PT buffer, and 100 μ l of ECL solution added to each well, followed by measurement of

Fig. 4. Purification of monoclonals to TIM3 using the colony screening methodology. (A and B). The indicated tagged (Fc or GST) canine TIM3 receptor (and control proteins) were coated onto immunoplate wells using alternating tags and subjected to four rounds of biopanning. Phage rounds screened (1–3) using alternating tagged TIM3 protein are in A or B. The data are plotted as M13 phage binding (in RLU) as a function of biopanning round and antigen coated; Fc-TIM3, GST-TIM3, GST-tagged scFv-PD1 [29], and Fc-tagged CTLA4. (C). Relative purity and electrophoretic migration of Fc-tagged or HIS-tagged canine TIM3 protein in a reducing and SDS denaturing gel. (D). To cross test, the phage pools isolated and sequenced by NGS, as in Fig. 3B, the round 3 and round 4 phage pools (both the Fc-GST-Fc-GST or the GST-Fc-GST-Fc screen) were assayed against either Fc tagged or his tagged canine TIM3 protein. The reason for doing so is that his tagged TIM3 is reported to be dimeric and it was important to determine whether the phage pools were able to bind to a third differently prepared canine TIM3 protein. (E). Individual colonies from one of the round 4 biopanning screens were processed to produce phage and these supernatants were assayed for activity towards canine TIM3. Out of 48 colonies approximately half displayed activity towards TIM3 protein. (F). Thirteen active antibodies from Fig. 4E were sequenced by the sanger method and the number of times they were identified by colony sequencing (column = colony sequencing) was compared to the number of NGS reads observed over round 1–4 based. (G). An example of the scFv sequences that emerge from some TIM3 clones from colony isolation including the pelB sequence, CDR domains, and C-terminal MYC tag.

luminescence using a Fluoroskan Ascent plate reader (PerkinElmer).

2.6. Assessing monoclonal antibody production in HEK293T cells

The three anti-TIM3 antibodies focused on; clones 11 (scFv-Fc-11), 26 (scFv-Fc-26 and IgG-29), and 29 (scFv-Fc-29 and IgG-29), were synthesized (TWIST Bioscience) in CMV expression plasmids (see Fig. 5A and B as representative gene structures). Plasmid map figures were generated using SnapGene software. The scFv-Fc fusions incorporated murine IgG2a sequences as the Fc domain, and the IgG expression plasmids were synthesized using two CMV promoters, one for each of the variable heavy chain fused to murine IgG2a Fc and the variable light chain fused to murine kappa light constant chain. The mouse constant domains were used because secondary reagents to this species are widely available (i.e. HRP conjugated anti-mouse antibody, DAKO P0260). The plasmids (1 µg) encoding the antibodies were transfected into 2 ml of confluent monolayer HEK293T cells (ATCC, CRL-11268) in DMEM plus 10 % FCS and incubated for three days at 37 °C. Media containing the secreted antibodies from HEK293T cells were tested by titration using ELISA (Fig. 5C and D). After coating Fc-TIM3 in immunoplates wells (1 µg/100 µl in sodium carbonate buffer (pH 9.0)) at 4 °C overnight, the wells were washed three times with 250 µl of PT buffer and then blocked using PTB buffer for 1 h. Media containing control media (no plasmid DNA transfected) or antibody gene transfected) was titrated in a final volume of 200 µl PTB buffer (Fig. 5C). After 1 h, the wells were washed three times using PT buffer followed by HRP-conjugated rabbit anti-mouse secondary antibody (1:000 dilution, DAKO, P0260). After washing three times with PT buffer, chemiluminescence solution was added and light was measured using a Fluoroskan plate reader (PerkinElmer).

2.7. ELISA assessment of TIM3 antibody binding activity after pretreatment of TIM3 protein with DTT

An ELISA was used to assess the impact of using DTT-treated TIM3 protein to alter antibody binding (Fig. 5D). A 96-well immunoplate was coated with Fc-TIM3 (1 µg/100 µl in sodium carbonate buffer (pH 9.0)) at 4 °C overnight. The wells were washed three times with 250 µl of PT buffer and then blocked using PTB buffer for 1 h. A solution of PTB was made with increasing amounts of DTT, from 0 to 100 mM (Fig. 5D) and incubated at room temperature for 60 min. Blocking buffer was then removed, the wells were washed three times with 250 µl of PT buffer, and then media from transfected HEK293T cells was added. From 1 µg of transfected DNA, the following dilutions were made in PTB buffer: scFv-Fc-11 (1:2 dilution), IgG-26 (1:2 dilution), scFv-Fc-29 (1:100 dilution), and IgG-29 (1:2 dilution). After 60 min, the wells were washed three times using PT buffer followed by the use of HRP-conjugated rabbit anti-mouse secondary antibody (1:000 dilution). After washing three times with PT buffer, chemiluminescence solution was added and light was measured using a Fluoroskan plate reader (PerkinElmer).

2.8. Antibody production in the ExpiCHO system

Purified antibodies were used to quantify input antibody for epitope mapping (Figs. 6 and 7), for flow cytometry (Fig. 10) and to measure the effects of the antibodies on the TIM3-GAL9 complex (Fig. 11). All antibodies were produced in the ExpiCHO system (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions using the max titer protocol. ExpiCHO cells were transfected with ExpiFectamine CHO Transfection Reagent and kept at 32 °C and 5 % CO₂ while rotating on an orbital shaker. After 10–14 days, the media containing secreted antibody was harvested and the antibody was purified using a 1 ml HiTrap protein A FF column (Cytiva, MA, USA) with an ÄKTA pure system (Cytiva). The supernatant was adjusted to pH 8.0 with a final Tris concentration of 0.1 M. This media fraction was passed through a 0.45 µm filter. The column was equilibrated with a buffer (0.1 M Tris pH 8.0), and the supernatant was applied, followed by washing with 0.1 M Tris pH 8 and finally with 0.01 M Tris pH 8. The antibody bound was eluted with a buffer composed of 0.1 M glycine pH 3. The eluate was immediately neutralized with 1 M Tris pH 8. The material was exchanged to PBS (pH 7.4) using a ZEBRA spin column (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The relative purity of a representative antibody preparation is shown in Fig. 6B.

2.9. Measurement of anti-TIM3 affinities by ELISA

TIM3-Fc was diluted to 1 µg ml⁻¹ in 100 mM carbonate buffer (pH 9.2), and 50 µl was added to each well of a 96 well immunoplate plate. Antigen was allowed to adsorb overnight at 4 °C. Wells were washed twice with 150 µl of PBST (0.1 % (v/v)) and blocked with 120 µl of PBST-BSA (3 % (w/v)) for 1 h. Antibodies were diluted in the same blocking buffer to generate titrations as indicated in Fig. 6C. Blocking buffer was removed from all wells, and 100 µl of each primary antibody was added, or blocking buffer only for negative control. Primary antibody was incubated for 1 h before washing four times with PBST. Rabbit anti-mouse (Dako P0260) was diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer, and 90 µl was added to each well and incubated for 1 h. Following incubation, all wells were washed four times with PBST as before. 75 µl of ECL was added to each well, and luminescence was measured using a Fluoroskan Ascent. Binding curve fitting to the data was performed as by Kemmer and Keller [30]. Concentration of antibody giving 50 % binding was thus determined, allowing measurement of relative affinity for the antigen.

2.10. ELISA and pepscan to localize the TIM3 epitope

Pepscan binding assays (Figs. 6 and 7) were performed with white 96-well High Protein Binding immunoplates. The wells were first coated with 1 µg of streptavidin in 100 µl of water overnight at 37°C. The wells were blocked with 250 µl of PTB. After washing three times with PT to remove residual streptavidin, 100 ng of the TIM3 biotinylated pepscan library was added per well (Figs. 6 and 7), diluted from 1 mg/ml DMSO stocks (Mimotopes, Australia) into 100 µl of a buffer containing PTB. After a 1 h incubation at room temperature and washing three times with PBT to remove unbound peptide, the indicated anti-TIM3 antibody

Fig. 5. Sensitivity of the epitopes of three TIM3-specific monoclonal antibodies to DTT. (A). General structure of the antibody expression gene of an scFv-Fc fusion, containing a fusion of Hc, Lc, and Fc (constant heavy) chain (murine IgG2a) using a single promoter (scFv-Fc-11 is shown here). (B). General structure of the antibody expression gene of an IgG showing variable heavy and light chains expressed with their respective constant domain chain fusions from separated CMV promoters and different polyA signals-bGH (for light chain) and SV40 (for heavy chain) (IgG-29 is shown here). (C). Media from HEK293 cells expressing these antibody genes was titrated using ELISA (volumes of 25, 50, or 100 µl) and antibody activity to canine TIM3 immobilized on the immunoplate wells was measured by ECL using a Fluoroskan Ascent FL (Labsystems, PerkinElmer). (D) Canine TIM3 protein was absorbed onto immunoplates and then incubated with the indicated amounts of DTT. After washing, the indicated antibodies were added to measure binding (in RLU) as a function of DTT concentration. Antibody binding activity to immobilized canine TIM3 was measured by ECL using a TECAN plate reader. (E). A model of canine TIM3 was constructed using ColabFold [36,37] with residues A24-R190 of UniProt entry A0A8C0QB74 [55]. Three possible di-sulfide bridges in canine TIM3 implicated in antibody binding to the respective epitopes are highlighted.

(1 µg/ml) was added in 100 µl of a buffer containing PTB for 1 h. After washing three times with PT, HRP-conjugated rabbit anti-mouse secondary antibody (DAKO, P0260) was added in 100 µl of a buffer containing PTB and incubated for 1 h. After washing three times with PT, chemiluminescence solution was added, and light was measured using a Fluoroskan plate reader (PerkinElmer) or an Infinite Mplex plate reader.

2.11. Assessment of human TIM3 cross-reactivity to anti-canine TIM3 antibodies by ELISA

Human TIM3 (Acro Biosystems, TI3-H82F8) and canine TIM3-Fc

were diluted in carbonate coating buffer (100 mM, pH 9.2) to 4, 1, and 0.25 µg ml⁻¹ 50 µl of each antigen was added to relevant wells in duplicates, with carbonate buffer only in control wells. Antigens were allowed to adsorb overnight at 4 °C. Wells were washed twice with 150 µl of PBST (0.1 % (v/v)), and blocked with 120 µl of PBST-BSA (3 % (w/v)) for 1 h. Blocking buffer was removed from all wells, and 100 µl of each primary antibody were added at 1 µg ml⁻¹, diluted in blocking buffer, or blocking buffer only for negative control. Primary antibodies were incubated for 1 h and were then washed four times with PBST. Rabbit anti mouse (Dako P0260) was diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer, and 90 µl was added to each well and incubated for 1 h. Following

A. Overlapping N-terminal biotinylated peptides (numbered 1-32)

B. Protein-A purified Mabs

C. Relative K_D for three of the purified antibodies

Antibody	K_D (nM)
scFv Fc 11	29.89
IgG 26	2.831
scFv Fc 29	24.55

D. ELISA using a pool of antibodies (scFv-Fc-11, scFv-Fc-29, IgG-26, IgG-29)

E. ELISA on peptides 11-15 and 22-26

F. Epitope peptides 12 + 14 and 23 + 25 location

(caption on next page)

Fig. 6. Epitope mapping using synthetic peptides. (A). A panel of overlapping synthetic peptides with an N-terminal biotin, an SGSG spacer, the indicated peptide sequence derived from TIM3, and a C-terminal amide were used in an ELISA format. (B). SDS polyacrylamide gel stained with Coomassie blue showing the relative mass of the individual Protein-A purified monoclonal antibodies. (C). ELISA format was employed to measure the affinity of the indicated purified antibodies for extracellular domain of TIM3 bound to a solid phase. The binding was measured across a concentration range of purified antibodies that allows a measurement of concentration giving 50 % of maximum binding. This generates an estimate of dissociation constant. Duplicate measurements are provided with data fitting as described [30]. (D). The binding of pooled TIM3 antibodies (scFv-Fc-11, scFv-Fc-29, IgG-26, and IgG29) to the pepscan is plotted as a function of the 32 different peptide sequences. (E). The binding of individual TIM3 antibodies (scFv-Fc-11, IgG-26, scFv-Fc-29, and IgG-29) to the pepscan series from the most bioactive peptide strings from part D (peptides 11–15 and 22–26). (F). Mapping of the epitope peptides to the using ColabFold [36,37] structure of TIM3. Red is peptide 12, Blue is Peptide 14, and the violet are peptides 23 and 25 mapping out with the structural domain. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

incubation, all wells were washed four times with PBST as before. 75 μ l of ECL was added to each well, and luminescence was measured using a Fluoroskan Ascent.

2.12. SDS-PAGE immunoblotting

Freestyle 293-F cells (ThermoFisher R79007) were cultured in suspension in Freestyle 293 Expression Medium (ThermoFisher 12338018). At a cell density of 1.0e6 cells per ml, 10 ml of culture was centrifuged to pellet cells. The cell pellet was resuspended in 1 ml of IGEAL lysis buffer (1 % IGEAL (v/v), 150 mM NaCl, 50 mM Tris HCl pH 8.0, 1x protease inhibitor mix) and incubated on ice for 30 min, with brief vortexing at 10-min intervals. The resulting lysate was centrifuged at 10,000 rcf for 10 min, 4 $^{\circ}$ C, and the solubilized protein in the supernatant was collected. For each lysate-containing sample for immunoblotting, 25 μ g of protein was used. 12.5–100 ng of TIM3-Fc was spiked into these 25 μ g lysate samples, as well as one lane containing 100 ng of TIM3-Fc without lysate. SDS loading buffer without reducing agent was added to each sample, which was then heated at 85 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 min. Samples were separated by electrophoresis on 10 % polyacrylamide gels and transferred to nitrocellulose membranes overnight. A separate lysate only sample was separated by electrophoresis and stained with Coomassie stain, and after destaining was imaged using an ImageQuant 800. Membranes were blocked with milk-PBST (5 % milk (w/v), 0.1 % Tween (v/v)) for 1 h, and primary antibodies were then added at 0.5 μ g/ml in blocking buffer. After 1 h incubation, membranes were washed 4 times for 3 min with PBST, before adding rabbit anti-mouse HRP (Dako P0260) diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer. Secondary antibody was incubated for 1 h, before washing 4 times for 3 min with PBST. ECL was added to the membranes for 1 min, then blotted dry and the membranes were imaged using an ImageQuant 800.

2.13. Flow cytometry

HCT-116 cells (Fig. 10B) were transfected either stably or transiently with untagged canine TIM3 expression plasmid (TWIST Bioscience, Fig. 10A). For stable transfection, cells were transfected using Lipofectamine 3000 transfection reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions and subsequently selected with G418 (500 μ g/ml) (GoldBio, St Louis, USA) for 7 days. For transient transfection, cells were transfected using polyethylenimine (PEI) (Polysciences, Warrington, USA) at a DNA to PEI ratio of 1:5 and analyzed by flow cytometry 24 h post-transfection. HCT-116 cells, stably or transiently transfected with untagged TIM3 expression plasmid, and HCT-116 control cells were trypsinized and washed with PBS followed by 20 min of blocking with 0.5 % BSA in PBS. Cells were then incubated with the anti-TIM3 IgG29 antibody (2.5 μ g/ml) in the blocking solution for 1 h on ice. After washing twice with PBS, cells were incubated with goat anti-mouse IgG (H + L) highly cross-adsorbed secondary antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 488 (cat. number A32723, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) diluted 1:1000 in the blocking solution for 30 min on ice. Following two final washes with PBS, cells were analyzed using a BD FACS Verse flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, USA) measuring Alexa Fluor 488 fluorescence signal. All samples were measured in duplicates. HCT-116 cells were from ATCC

(CCL-247), and the OVC-cOSA-31 cell line was previously reported by Geoffrey Wood (University of Guelph, Canada) [31].

3. Results

3.1. Purification of tagged TIM3 protein from eukaryotic expression systems

Antibodies can be produced by immunization of animals using protein antigens that are mixed with adjuvant. These might typically partially denature the antigen resulting in the acquisition of antibodies that bind linear epitopes on denatured proteins. The method however does not preclude the acquisition of antibodies with complex conformational epitopes due to local secondary structures including discontinuous epitopes [32]. By contrast, *in vitro* screening of a biologics phage display library against an antigen can exploit buffer conditions and/or protein production methodologies that can produce or maintain native or folded conformations of a bait protein antigen and/or include the presence of co-factors that stabilize different conformations of an antigen [33].

Transmembrane receptors like TIM3 are relatively more difficult to purify in a native state from bacterial expression systems because they often require particular disulfide arrangements that maintain the native structure, thus precluding the use of robust bacterial expression systems [34]. To increase the probability of the acquisition of antibodies to the native conformation of the TIM3 receptor, the extracellular domain of canine TIM3 was C-terminally fused to human Fc or GST and was purified from the media after it was secreted from HEK293 cells (Fig. 1A and B). The assembly and secretion of proteins from this mammalian cell model is more likely to result in the production of native protein with the correct disulfide combination.

3.2. A high throughput NGS methodology to measure efficiency of biopanning

The TIM3 receptor fusions thus acquired were coated onto immunoplates and subjected to four rounds of biopanning using alternating tagged proteins. This increases the probability that we would isolate pools of scFv -phage fusions that exhibited binding to the antigen but not the Fc or GST tag (Fig. 2A). The parental scFv library composed of the naïve BCR repertoire from canine tissue [29] was used in a first-round screen using Fc-tagged TIM3, the second round using GST-tagged TIM3, the third-round protein using Fc-tagged TIM3, and the fourth round using GST-tagged TIM3. The phage pools from these four rounds of biopanning were then assayed using next-generation short-read DNA sequencing (NGS) to measure the high throughput depth of enrichment of scFv antibodies, as a function of the rounds of biopanning, via CDR3 domain sequencing (Fig. 3). The strengths and weaknesses of the NGS methodology is briefly summarized in Fig. 2B. The phage pools from each round were spiked directly into PCR reactions using forward primers that target PelB-FR1 boundary sequences of the scFv gene (Fig. 2C-i) and reverse bar-coded primers that are proximal to the FR3-CDR3-FR4 boundary sequence (Fig. 2C-ii). There are four reverse bar-coded primers for each bar-coded pool (Fig. 2C-ii), with the degenerate DNA sequences used in attempts to capture as much FR4

A. Overlapping biotinylated peptide-12 alanine scan mutagenesis

73-NLKYQTSNRYRLMRN-wt Pep-12
 NAKYQTSNRYRLMRN-L74A
 NLAYQTSNRYRLMRN-K75A
 NLKAQTSNRYRLMRN-Y76A
 NLKYATSNRYRLMRN-Q77A
 NLKYQASNRYRLMRN-T78A
 NLKYQTANRYRLMRN-S79A
 NLKYQTSARYRLMRN-N80A
 NLKYQTSNAYRLMRN-R81A
 NLKYQTSNRARLMRN-Y82A
 NLKYQTSNRYALMRN-R83A
 NLKYQTSNRYRAMRN-L84A
 NLKYQTSNRYRLARN-M85A
 NLKYQTSNRYRLMAN-R86A
 NLKYQTSNRYRLMRA-N87A

B-E. ELISA using an Alanine scan of peptide-12

F. Views of the Epitope peptide-12 (red) in relation to disulfide bonds (yellow)

Fig. 7. Alanine scan mutagenesis of the dominant epitope at peptide-12. (A). A panel of synthetic peptides derived from peptide-12 (Fig. 6) with a scan of alanine mutations with an N-terminal biotin, an SGSG spacer, and a C-terminal amide were used in an ELISA format. (B-E). The binding of individual anti-TIM3 antibodies (scFv-Fc-11, scFv-Fc-29, IgG-26, and IgG-29) to the pepscan is plotted as a function of the positions where the alanine amino acid replacement was introduced vs the wild-type peptide sequence (WT). The red asterisk marks amino acids whose mutation to alanine results in attenuated antibody binding at ~0.5 or lower. The green asterisk marks amino acids whose mutation to alanine results in enhanced antibody binding at >1.0. The double red asterisk marks amino acids whose mutation to alanine results in attenuated antibody binding with a relative specificity for scFv-Fc-11. F. A view of the dominant peptide binding regions (peptide 12 in and 14 in blue) in relation to the position of the disulfide bonds using TIM3 structure defined using ColabFold [36,37]. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

A. Divergence of the peptide-12 MAB contact sites in selected mammals

Canis_lupus_dingo	RNLKYQTSNRYRLMRNFHKGDVSLTI
Panthera_onca	RNLKYQTSNRYQLKRNFKHKGDVSLTI
Equus_asinus	RNLKYQISSRYRLMGHLYKGDVSLTI
Sus_scrofa	RNMKYRTSSRYLLKRNVHKGDVTLTI
Monodon_monoceros	RNLNYWTSSRYLLKRNFKHKGDVTLTI
Delpinapterus_leucas	RNLTYWTSSRYLLKRNFKHKGDVTLTI
Balaenoptera_acutorostrata	RNLSYRTSSRYLLKRNFRKGDVTLTI
Pan_troglodytes	RDVNYRTS-RYWLNKDFRKGDVSLTI
Nomascus_leucogenys	RDVNYRTSSRYWLNKDFHKGDVSLTI
Homo_sapiens	RDVNYWTS-RYWLNKDFRKGDVSLTI
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B. Analysis of antibody binding to human and canine TIM3

Fig. 8. Analysis of antibody binding to human and canine TIM3. (A). The major peptide epitope (peptide 12) was compared to other mammalian species as indicated to identify sites of identity and divergence. (B). An ELISA was used to compare the relative binding of the indicated antibodies to canine or human TIM3. After coating the indicated amounts of canine or human TIM3, antibodies were added, and binding was measured using anti-mouse HRP conjugated antibody. Antibody binding activity was measured by ECL using a Fluoroskan plate reader. Data are plotted as antibody binding (RLU) as a function of protein titration (canine or human TIM3) and antibody type.

diversity as possible (Fig. 2C–iii).

The amplicons from PCR reactions were separated by agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig. 2D). The ~500 bp amplicons were purified from agarose gels and subjected to QC analysis prior to blunt end-ligation of the Illumina sequencing adaptors (data not shown). The amplicons were blunt end ligated to the new generation of Illumina adaptor primers and subjected to deep DNA sequencing. The top >1,000,000 sequences were selected (Supplementary Table 1) and analyzed for CDR3 DNA reads as a function of biopanning rounds with the parental library as the negative control (Fig. 3). A small subset of the enriched sequences (in the gene structure of Fig. 3A) from Supplementary Table 1 are shown in Fig. 3B.

The most highly enriched antibody clone isolated based on CDR3 sequencing (scFv-11 clone) appears in round 4 with 4,509,828

sequencing reads (Fig. 3B). Based on the total read number in round 4 (6,007,650 reads), this single clone represents ~ 75 % of the total NGS sequencing reads and ~555.7x enrichment relative to abundance of this sequence based on reads from the parental library (Fig. 3B). The second most abundant CDR3 represented by scFv-5, was also enriched in rounds 3 and 4 (read numbers = 213,947 and 299,982). The round 4 scFv-5 sequencing reads were 291.8x enrichment over the parental reads of 1028. Other sequences are also highlighted in Fig. 3B, with the fold enrichment reduced as the round 4 read number was shown to decrease.

These data give a deeper quantitative view of enrichment efficiency based on CDR3 sequencing as a function of biopanning rounds. The plot (Fig. 3C) highlights the dominance of scFv-11 sequences emerging in rounds 3 and 4. These PCR-NGS methodologies are a relatively rapid

A. Pure protein

B. Pure protein spiked into lysate

(caption on next page)

Fig. 9. Immunoblotting with the anti-TIM3 antibodies. (A). His-tagged or Fc-tagged TIM3 proteins (1 μ g per lane) were processed using denaturing gel electrophoresis without the inclusion of DTT. The membranes were blotted with the indicated antibodies and processed using HRP-conjugated anti-mouse IgG and TMB colorimetric development solution. B. Immunoblots of HEK293 lysates spiked with recombinant Human Fc-tagged canine TIM3 protein. Left lane is the protein standard. First sample lane is 100 ng of TIM3 in the absence of lysate. Remaining lanes are indicated amounts of TIM3 diluted in 25 μ g of protein from HEK293 lysates. The asterisk marks the position of the mobility of Fc-tagged TIM3, after electrophoresis in the absence of reducing agent in the SDS gel. The indicated primary antibodies were used at 0.5 μ g/ml. Anti-mouse HRP conjugated antibody was added and activity was measured by ECL. The far-right panel shows a Coomassie stained SDS-PAGE of the cellular lysate protein content.

way to assess the efficiency of biopanning in a quantitative manner. Because the biopanning against TIM3 appeared to identify dominant clones by rounds 3 or 4 using NGS (Fig. 3C), we next used colony isolation methodologies to identify and sanger sequence individual monoclonal antibodies. In addition, because the use of PCR-NGS is a relatively recent methodology used to measure biopanning efficiency [29], we also aimed to determine whether the distribution of colony sequences mirrored the NGS data (Fig. 3B).

3.3. Using low throughput colony screening to isolate TIM3 reactive antibodies

The NGS sequencing data in Fig. 3B used the biopanning approach which involved screening against alternating Fc-GST-Fc-GST tagged TIM3 from rounds 1–4. In addition to this screen, we also biopanned against alternating GST-Fc-GST-Fc tagged TIM3 to determine whether bioactive pools of scFv phage could be measured using this approach. We first measured phage pools screened against alternating Fc-GST-Fc tagged TIM3 from rounds 1–3, for whether they bind to either Fc-TIM3, GST-TIM3, GST-scFv-PD1 [29], or Fc-CTLA4. The phage from the Fc-GST-Fc biopanning were shown to yield active scFv phage by round 3 (Fig. 4A, gray bars). The round 3 spike in activity towards Fc-TIM3 or GST-TIM3 (Fig. 4A, gray bars) mirrors the dominant enrichment of unique CDR3s observed in round 3 using NGS methods (Fig. 3B and Supplementary Table 1). For example, 886 scFv5 sequences were measured in Round 2 phage, with this value increasing to 213,947 reads by Round 3 (Fig. 3B). The data also show a degree of specificity because the phage pools did not bind to GST-scFv-PD1 or Fc-CTLA4 (Fig. 4A), indicating that there were minimal antibodies selected against the GST or Fc tags.

Screening the other way around; biopanning against alternating GST-Fc-GST-Fc tagged TIM3 (Fig. 4B), there was similarly phage from round 3 of this biopanning pool that were shown to yield active scFv phage (Fig. 4B, gray bars). The data also show a degree of specificity because the phage pools did not bind to GST-scFv-PD1 or Fc-CTLA4 (Fig. 4B), indicating that there were minimal scFv antibodies enriched against the GST or Fc tags.

We also cross referenced the activity of these phage pools by assaying their activity on a differentially tagged protein that was not used in the initial screen, his-tagged canine TIM3, which migrates in the format of a dimer using native chromatography and SDS gel electrophoresis (Fig. 4C, lane 3). The molecular mass of this extracellular TIM3 fragment is \sim 17 kDa (amino acids 24–189). The mobility of the his-tagged TIM3 on the SDS gel is approximately 40–45 kDa suggesting it is an oligomer (dimer). Regardless, this dimeric or oligomeric form of his-tagged TIM3 is recognized by phage from round 3 or round 4 pools (Fig. 4D). However, we observed a relatively lower signal using the alternating format GST-Fc-GST-Fc (Fig. 4D, right panel). In addition, the his-tagged TIM3 receptor displayed lower binding capacity to the round 3 or round 4 phage pools, relative to Fc-TIM3 receptor (Fig. 4D, blue vs orange bar graphs). This could be due to several factors; the dimer in the his-tagged formulation might block dominant epitopes, the his-tagged protein might not adsorb to the solid phase as well as Fc-tagged TIM3 receptor, or the dimeric nature of the Fc fusion protein elevates avidity by creating a ‘bivalent’ TIM3 epitope.

Nevertheless, there are antibodies in the round 3 or round 4 phage pools which bind his-tagged TIM3, verifying specificity. The scFv-phage pool from the Fc-GST-Fc alternating screen was plated for individual

colony isolation and bioactive scFv were assayed in an ELISA (Fig. 4E). From 48 colonies, we acquired over 20 active monoclonal scFv phages. Upon sequencing of the monoclonals, we acquired six distinct antibodies (Fig. 4F). We could have screened and sequenced more colonies to isolate additional sequences; however, this low throughput method identified a sufficient number of antibodies to progress.

One aim of this study was to integrate the high throughput NGS methodology to the low throughput colony screening method (Fig. 2B). The strength of the former is that biopanning efficiency can be quantified as a function of rounds (as in Fig. 3C). When examining the overlap, one key thing to note is that the scFv-11 sequence dominated in both NGS and colony screening (Fig. 4F), where 6 out of 13 TIM3-reactive scFv phage clones had the same CDR3 as the most abundant by NGS (Fig. 4F; 4,509,828 reads by round 4). The next most abundant clone by NGS (scFv-5; 299,982 reads by round 4) was observed once by colony screening (Fig. 4F). However, the other sequences isolated by colony screening were not well represented by NGS. For example, scFv29 and scFv28 were each observed twice (Fig. 4F). However, scFv-29 was not enriched above parental library in round 2 (3 reads in round 4 vs 45 parental reads, Fig. 4F). These data suggest that although scFv-29 is a relatively dominant clone based on colony isolation, there appears to be a negative bias in amplification of scFv-29 sequences using the primers from Fig. 2C. Similarly, scFv-26 is observed only once by colony screening but is not well enriched in round 4 PCR vs parental library (102 reads in round 4 vs 40 parental reads, Fig. 4F). scFv-28 is enriched in round 4 vs parental library (11 reads in round 4 vs 0 parental reads, Fig. 4F). However, it is remarkable that 2 of these sequences were isolated using colony screening. Together these data indicate that the NGS method is an approach which can rapidly quantify the efficiency of CDR3 enrichment as a function of rounds of biopanning (Fig. 3C). However, any individual scFv that is identified by colony screening (such as clone 28) may not be well amplified using the PCR primer set used (Fig. 2C). An example of the gene structure of two of these antibodies is listed in Fig. 4G.

3.4. Activity of TIM3 antibodies in orthogonal formats: creating expression plasmids for use in eukaryotic cells

Of these six sequences encoding active antibodies (Fig. 4F), we focused on three: (i) the most abundant one identified by both NGS and colony screening (scFv-11); (ii) a relatively abundant clone by colony screening but not amplified by NGS (scFv-29); and (iii) a rare clone based on NGS but identified in the colony screening (scFv-26).

All three antibodies were synthesized into mammalian expression vectors as either scFv-Fc fusions (Fig. 5A) or as IgG using dual promoter expression vectors (Fig. 5B). Both are chimeric IgG with mouse constant regions for compatibility with readily available secondary reagents. These chimeric IgG expressing plasmids encoded the heavy and light chain on the same plasmid, from separated promoters and the heavy chain used a SV40 polyA tail whilst the light chain used a bGH polyA tail (Fig. 5B).

All these murine-canine chimeric antibodies were active when expressed from plasmids in HEK293T cells (Fig. 5C). scFv-Fc-29 was the most active single chain fusion upon titration of media in a dose-dependent manner (Fig. 5C). scFv-Fc-26 was weakly active as a single chain fusion but exhibited dose-dependent activity upon titration of the media (Fig. 5C). scFv-Fc-11 fusion was weakly active and did not show dose-dependent activity upon titration of the media (Fig. 5C).

A. Full-length TIM3 expression plasmid

B. IgG-29 binding to TIM3 transfected human cells

Fig. 10. IgG-29 Binds to canine TIM3 in flow cytometry. (A). General structure of the canine untagged full-length TIM3 expression plasmid. (B). Live human HCT-116 cells were incubated with ExpiCHO-produced, purified anti-TIM3 IgG-29, followed by anti-mouse Alexa-488 conjugated secondary antibody for flow cytometry. HCT-116 control cells were used along with cells stably transfected and transiently transfected (using PEI) with a canine TIM3 expression plasmid.

Upon conversion to a chimeric IgG, with murine constant heavy and light chain domains (Fig. 5B), IgG-29 was as active as scFv-Fc-29 (Fig. 5C), IgG-26 showed more activity than scFv-Fc-26 (Fig. 5C), and scFv-Fc-11 was not active in the IgG format (data not shown). It is not necessarily uncommon for scFv to IgG conversions to be inactive; a recent report highlighted a scFv to canine PD1 that required FR mutations to be introduced allowing activity within an IgG structure [35].

We did not quantify the antibody produced from media in Fig. 5C which was not possible due to the use of full serum containing media (10 % serum); the purpose of this experiment was to ask whether the plasmids produce any active antibody. Thus, the units in Fig. 5C are presented as activity per unit volume and we titrated the volume (from 25 to 100 μ l) to determine whether there was a dose dependence. Because all three antibodies are active, the subsequent experiments (in

A. Dose dependent binding of TIM3 to GAL9

METHOD

1. BIND 250ng (7 pmol) GAL9 to plate in 100 ul
2. Titrate TIM3-FC (5.8 pmol(300 ng), 1.9 pmol(100 ng), 0.58 pmol (30 ng)) for 60 min
3. Add goat anti-human FC Ab
4. Add HRP conjugated Rb anti-Goat IgG

B. Dose dependent binding of CHO cell expressed anti-TIM3 Ab to TIM3

METHOD

1. BIND 300ng (5.8 pmol) TIM3 to plate
2. Titrate anti-TIM3 Mouse Fc chimeric Ab's for 60 min
3. Add HRP conjugated goat anti-Mouse IgG

C. Anti-TIM3 Ab's attenuate TIM3 binding to GAL9

METHOD

1. BIND 250ng (7 pmol) GAL9 to plate in 100 ul
2. Add 300 ng TIM3-Fc (5.8 pmol) for 60 min without or with a pre-incubation with the indicated antibodies in 100 ul
3. The antibody amounts were 3.3 pmol (33 nM) and 6.6 pmol (66 nM) to give a ratio of MAB:TIM3 of 0.56 and 1.1, respectively.
4. Add goat anti-human FC Ab
5. Add HRP conjugated Rb anti-Goat IgG

Fig. 11. The effects of anti-TIM3 antibodies on the GAL9-TIM3 complex. (A). An ELISA was set up that optimized the binding of TIM3 to GAL9. Human Fc-tagged canine TIM3 was incubated at either 30 (0.58 pmol), 100 (1.9 pmol), or 300 ng (5.8 pmol) with 250 ng (7 pmol) of GAL9 on the solid phase. The ratio of TIM3:GAL9 on this assay ranges from 0.05, 0.17, and 0.54. Binding of TIM3 to GAL9 was measured using a goat anti-human FC antibody followed by HRP conjugated rabbit anti-goat antibody. Binding of TIM3 is plotted (in RLU) as a function of TIM3 protein levels. (B). The relative binding of ExpiCHO purified antibodies to optimize amounts of purified antibody for the GAL9-TIM3 protein interaction assay in C. Antibody genes were transfected into ExpiCHO cells and purified from the cell culture supernatant (Fig. 6B). Human Fc-tagged canine TIM3 was coated onto wells, and then increasing amounts of each antibody was added, followed by HRP-conjugated rabbit anti-mouse Fc antibody. Binding of Antibodies to TIM3 is plotted (in RLU) as a function of antibody protein levels. (C). The effects of antibody pre-incubation on the TIM3-GAL9 complex. Following GAL9 (7 pmol) adsorption on the immunoplate wells, the indicated, purified antibodies were incubated with fixed TIM3 protein (5.8 pmol) in PBS+0.1 %Tween-20-3 %BSA for 30 min prior to addition to the wells. After 60 min, the binding of Human Fc-tagged canine TIM3 to GAL9 was measured using a goat anti-human FC antibody followed by HRP conjugated rabbit anti-goat antibody. Binding of TIM3 is plotted (in RLU) as a function of antibody absence or presence.

Figs. 6–11) were performed after purification of the antibodies in serum free media using a Protein A column.

3.5. Activity of TIM3 antibodies in orthogonal formats: epitope sensitivity to reducing agent

One of the advantages of screening for antibodies towards antigens *in vitro* is that the bait antigen conformation can be controlled. In the case of extracellular receptors, one way to obtain soluble, native antigens is to produce the protein in human cells and purified from secreted media. Because receptors are often folded into native conformations through the maintenance of disulfide bonds, we screened for whether redox state effects the epitope of the antibody. In Fig. 5D, we preincubated the TIM3 receptor with increasing concentrations of DTT disrupting native disulfide bonds. The data show that scFv-Fc-11, scFv-Fc-29, IgG-29, and IgG-26 are all reduced in binding to TIM3 upon DTT titration from ~6 to 100 mM. The possible cysteine residues within disulphide bonds which maintain the TIM3 epitopes are shown in Fig. 5E; this is a Colabfold generated model of the canine TIM3 IgV-like domain and adjacent unstructured regions [36,37].

3.6. Activity of TIM3 antibodies in orthogonal formats: epitope mapping using synthetic peptides

Despite the possibility that the epitopes are conformationally sensitive and/or discontinuous, we assayed the ability of the anti-TIM3 antibodies to bind to overlapping peptides derived from the TIM3 receptor using ELISA (Fig. 6A). To measure quantitative effects of antibody on binding to synthetic peptides, we purified the antibodies from ExpiCHO cells (Fig. 6B). The relative K_D was measured for three of these four antibodies (Fig. 6C). ELISA was used as it has been previously evaluated as a method to complement SPR to define the K_D of an antibody-antigen complex [38,39]. IgG-26 exhibited the lowest relative K_D (2.8 nM), with scFv-Fc-11 and scFv-Fc-29 being weaker but relatively similar at 29.8 nM and 24.5 nM, respectively (Fig. 6C). IgG-29 was not amenable to production in sufficient soluble quantities for K_d measurements, with visual evidence of aggregation at high concentrations (data not shown).

These antibodies were all pooled into one aliquot, creating a 'poly-clonal' antibody pool. This poly-antibody fraction was added to immunoplate wells and binding to the individual pepscan library was accessed (Fig. 6D). The most dominant overlapping peptides were identified at 12 and 14 with minor overlapping peptides identified at peptides 23 and 25.

The dominant series of peptides (peptides 11–15 and 22–26) were then re-assayed using the individual purified antibodies to normalize the input antibodies and determine whether they bind to the same dominant peptides (Fig. 6E). All antibodies exhibited relatively equivalent binding for peptide 12 over peptide 14 at the antibody concentration of 1 μ g/ml (Fig. 6E). Shared core amino acids within these two peptides are shown in Fig. 6A, RLMRN. However, peptide-13 (which also contains the RLMRN motif) did not bind. These data suggest that this shared motif does not form the epitope and that the epitope is therefore discontinuous being composed of elements within peptide-12 and peptide-14. Peptides 23 and 25 which might exhibit an intrinsically disordered epitopes out with the structural domain (Fig. 6F) were not further analyzed here.

Given the dominant epitope appeared within peptide-12, alanine scan mutagenesis of epitope peptide 12 (Fig. 7A) was performed to determine if amino acid contact points could be defined and if they are overlapping or distinct (Fig. 7A). There are shared and distinct features between the antibodies' binding to these alanine scan peptides, suggesting two different epitope classes are present. First, the shared features include the attenuated binding upon mutation of K75, R81, R83, and R86 (Fig. 7B–E, red asterisks). Differences exist in scFv-Fc-11 which was also attenuated in binding to peptides with mutations at Y76, Q77, or Y82 (Fig. 7B, double red asterisks). This contrasts with IgG-26 and IgG-29, both of which were stimulated in binding to peptides with

the mutation of Q77 (Fig. 7C and E, green asterisks).

The attenuated binding of scFv-Fc-11 by mutation in Q77 was not due to the scFv-Fc scaffold itself, since the scFv version of IgG-29 mirrored the stimulatory effects on IgG-29 (compare Fig. 7D to E, green asterisks at Q77). scFv-Fc-11 was also not stimulated in binding by mutation of L74 as the other three were (Fig. 7C–E, green asterisks). However, all four murine-canine chimeric antibodies were stimulated in binding by mutation of L84 and M85 (Fig. 7B–E). Together, these data demonstrate that all four antibodies that contact peptide-12 share a core interaction around K75, R81, R83, and R86. However, unique and major differences between clone 11 and clones 26/29 are the gain of function binding contacts, suggesting differences in the two epitopes classes. The proximity of cysteine residues to the epitope is shown in Fig. 7F.

It was important to examine whether these monoclonal antibodies could bind to human TIM3, as a cross-reactive antibody would provide a biologic with direct translation to the human system. The relative divergence of amino acids at the dominant peptide-12 epitope are shown in Fig. 8A. When all four anti-TIM3 antibodies were used to measure binding as a function of increasing amounts of canine or human TIM3 (Fig. 8B), scFv-Fc-11 and IgG-29 displayed relatively low affinity for human TIM3. By contrast, IgG-26 and scFv-Fc-29 display a small degree of binding to human TIM3 (Fig. 8B). Nevertheless, the substantially reduced binding of all four antibodies to human TIM3 might be explained by the divergence at these four positions with the dominant epitope in peptide-12: K75 N, R83W, M85 N, and R86G (Fig. 8A vs Fig. 7B–E). These data suggest that these antibodies might not be convertible for human therapeutics without substantial mutagenesis. In a parallel project we have also isolated antibodies to human TIM3, and these antibodies do not share CDR3 sequence similarity to the canine-specific anti-TIM3 antibodies (data not shown).

3.7. Activity of TIM3 antibodies in orthogonal formats: immunoblotting

Purified Fc-tagged TIM3 or HIS-tagged TIM3 were immunoblotted with the indicated murine-canine chimeric antibodies using SDS buffer without DTT (Fig. 9A). All three antibodies bound similarly to each tagged protein (Fig. 9A, lanes 3–8), relative to the control secondary antibody (Fig. 9A, lanes 1 and 2). We were unable to determine if the epitopes for all three antibodies sequences were different based on proteolytic fingerprinting using the SDS gel method. The treatment of Fc-tagged TIM3 receptor with increasing proteinase K or ENDO-gluC to produce proteolytic fingerprints abrogated the binding of the anti-TIM3 antibodies to the fragmented protein (data not shown). This indicates that the protease eliminates the epitope.

We next wanted to evaluate the specificity of the purified antibodies to TIM3 protein in the presence of proteins in crude lysates to evaluate their specificity and sensitivity using the immunoblot format. Decreasing amounts of purified Fc-TIM3 protein were spiked into lysates from human HEK293 cells and immunoblotted to estimate the specificity upon competition with cellular proteins (Fig. 9B). The antibodies do display differences in apparent affinity. scFv-Fc-11 gives rise to the weakest immunoblot signal with a sensitivity down to 25 ng (Fig. 9B–I). scFv-Fc-29 gives rise to the highest sensitivity down to 12.5 ng (Fig. 9B–III), followed by IgG-26 (Fig. 9B–III), and then IgG-29 (Fig. 9B–IV). A Coomassie blue gel of the spiked lysates are shown in the inset on the right of Fig. 9B. Together, these data suggest that the antibodies are relatively specific for TIM3 when in competition with other proteins from a cellular lysate bound to the nitrocellulose membrane.

3.8. Activity of TIM3 antibodies in orthogonal formats: flow cytometry

Since the antibody epitopes are sensitive to DTT it remained possible that the TIM3 receptor on the cell surface, embedded within the plasma membrane, might have an altered conformation compared to the extracellular domain we use for our biochemical characterizations. As

such, human HCT116 colon cancer cells (which do not express canine TIM3) were used as a model. Cells were either used as stable TIM3 clones or transiently transfected with TIM3 expression plasmids (Fig. 10A) and then IgG-29 binding was measured by flow cytometry. IgG-29 was used, as it produced the highest yield of purified antibody with equimolar heavy and light chains in ExpiCHO cells (Fig. 6B). In addition, IgG-29 was generally the most active antibody we characterized (Figs. 5–7) even though it appears to aggregate and becomes insoluble at higher concentrations (as described in Fig. 6C) when purified using low pH elution from a Protein A column. The data show that HCT116 cells transfected with full-length untagged canine TIM3 are bound by IgG-29 (Fig. 10B). Similarly, using stable TIM3 transfectants of HCT116 (Fig. 10B), IgG-29 was shown to bind although with a lower signal presumably due to lower receptor expression. We were also able to measure binding of IgG-26 and IgG-29 to a TIM3 transfected OVC-cOSA-31 [31] canine cancer cell line (data not shown), indicating that both IgG forms could be also used in canine cell models.

3.9. Activity of TIM3 antibodies in orthogonal formats: effects on TIM3 binding to GAL9

TIM3 can suppress the apoptotic effectiveness of Galectin-9 (GAL9) [25]. Accordingly, it was finally of interest to determine whether the antibodies impact the stability of the TIM3-GAL9 complex *in vitro*. The binding of Fc-tagged TIM3 to GAL9 (250 ng per well or 7 pmol) could be detected in an immunoplate format, with a dose dependent signal observed upon titration of 30–300 ng TIM3 (from 0.58 pmol to 5.8 pmol) per well (Fig. 11A). Activity was measured using an anti-human Fc antibody which would not interfere with our testing of the TIM3 antibodies, which have an anti-murine constant domain (Fc).

Having established the binding of TIM3 to GAL9, we next quantified the optimal amount of each murine-canine chimeric antibody required to bind to TIM3. Purified antibodies from ExpiCHO cells (as in Fig. 6B) to obtain sufficient protein for evaluating the binding of TIM3 to GAL9. All four murine-canine chimeric antibodies exhibited equivalent dose-dependent binding to fixed amounts of Fc-tagged TIM3 (Fig. 11B).

The immunoplate format was next used to measure the effects of the murine-canine chimeric antibodies on the stability of the TIM3-GAL9 complex. The steps were: 250 ng of GAL9 (7 pmol and no GAL9 control) was coated per immunoplate well. After blocking, 300 ng (5.8 pmol) of TIM3 (and no TIM3 control) was added per reaction, and then either 500 ng (3.3 pmol) or 1 μ g (6.6 pmol) of the purified murine-canine chimeric antibodies (and a no antibody control) were added per reaction to produce a 0.56 and or 1.1:1 ratio of antibody:TIM3 antigen. Under these conditions, there was a dose dependent attenuation of TIM3 binding to GAL9 (Fig. 11C). This is consistent with the generally overlapping specificity of all purified antibodies to the dominant epitope face in peptide-12 but also including peptide-14 (Figs. 6 and 7).

At the ratio of 0.56:1 (3.3 pmol antibody:5.8 pmol TIM3), the % inhibition of all four antibodies as an aggregate is 64.8 %. At the ratio of 1.1:1 (6.6 pmol antibody:5.8 pmol TIM3), the % inhibition of all four antibodies as an aggregate is 77.1 %. There is a kinetic component to the assay, as the incubation times were relatively short. The pre-incubation of antibody and TIM3 was 30 min at room temperature which allows time for binding of the antibody-antigen complex. The next stage of the incubations then involves addition to reactions with GAL9 on the solid phase where competition for binding then begins between TIM3-GAL9 and TIM3-antibodies for 60 min.

4. Discussion

TIM3 is a component of an immune checkpoint pathway in mammals [7]. Although PD-1 and CTLA-4 have historically been the focus of immunotherapies, recent data has shown that canine cancers have a striking pan-cancer expression of TIM3 coding mRNA [28]. These data highlight the opportunity for TIM3 directed immunotherapies for use in

veterinary oncology. In this report, next-generation sequencing and standard phage screening methodologies have been used to acquire a monoclonal antibody panel specific to canine TIM3. The phage library was derived from a recently assembled canine naïve scFv-phage library [29]. Two prior reports have demonstrated the feasibility of developing canine antibodies for immune checkpoint antibody therapeutics: one approach used a canine scFv library prepared from different canine patient samples to acquire antibodies to canine PD-1 [29,35] and another study which dogized a hybridoma-derived antibody to canine PD1 [40].

A question can be raised as to whether naïve phage antibody libraries would have a repertoire of antibodies that can bind to self-antigens due to negative selection pressures during B-cell development [41], especially such as those involved in the immune system control such as PD-1 or TIM3. However, several previous studies can be used to counter this concern. First, because a fraction of randomly assembled antibody gene segments yield a substantial number of antibody genes with potential for self-antigen reactivity during early B cell development, it is possible that the naïve scFv library we and others clone from canine animals [29,42] also harbor populations of antibody genes that can bind to self-antigens. Thus, although it might be counter intuitive that it is possible to develop canine antibodies specific for canine antigens, a similar ability to acquire human antibodies to human target antigens has also emerged [43]. In addition to the possibility that developmental stages of B-cell populations can impact on self-antigen antibody acquisition, a recent study has also shown that cancer patients might also produce antibodies to self-cancer antigens [8]. These data together suggest that antibody library gene cloning from B-cell populations can capture variable domains capable of self-species reactivity.

The use of this naïve scFv library against native, folded canine TIM3 receptor has allowed the isolation of over a dozen novel antibodies to both canine and human TIM3 (data not shown). An interesting feature of the three antibodies we have characterized to canine TIM3, is that all epitopes appear to center around a common structural or conformational motif (Fig. 6E). Next generation deep sequencing also identified rare scFv clones (Fig. 3), but we did not clone these out and it remains possible that these antibodies bind different epitopes. The epitope of the antibodies we did scale up are all also abrogated by pre-treatment of the TIM3 receptor with a dithiol (Fig. 5). The conformational sensitivity of the receptor to reducing agent highlights the utility of initiating an antibody discovery screen using native receptors assembled and expressed in mammalian cells. Although there are not many studies documenting di-sulfide dependencies in antibody epitopes, one prior example highlighted an antibody specific for the insulin receptor whose epitope was compromised by reducing agent [44] and another study in which an antibody epitope within a malarial antigen was sensitive to disruption of disulfides [45].

Although the anti-TIM3 antibodies bind to individual peptides derived from the TIM3 open reading frame, the binding did not precisely overlap because peptide 13 does not bind under conditions in which peptide 12 and peptide 14 do bind (Fig. 6). As such, we might consider that the epitopes form weak linear motifs or discontinuous epitopes. DTT treated TIM3 receptor (–/+ SDS) does not bind to the antibodies, despite, presumably, any linear motifs would have been exposed to solvent in the presence of DTT. In addition, our routine use of peptide-phage display to define antibody epitopes [46], did not identify a linear peptide sequence of selectable affinity to the purified TIM3 antibodies (data not shown). Thus, the epitopes appear to be largely discontinuous or conformational because the epitope primarily depends on the native disulfide bonds imbedded in a region with β -sheets and disulfide fixed architecture within the IgV domain of TIM3 (Fig. 6F). A report dissecting the epitopes of hundreds of antibodies with ‘conformational’ contacts used an algorithm that quantifies an epitope as straight, curved, or folded, finding that only 4 % form truly linear epitopes [47] even if conformational epitopes have a degree of linear specificity built-in. We would therefore consider that the antibodies we

isolated to TIM3 have some linear amino acid component within the constrained contact sites, as evidence by the alanine scan mutagenesis data (Fig. 7). It has been noted that different antibodies binding to the same linear peptide sequence can induce different conformations of the peptide [48].

Caninized monoclonal antibodies are now emerging as potentially powerful biologics for use in treating canine cancers as well as informing human immunotherapy models. Not only have CTLA-4 canine antibodies been developed [49] and canine PD-1 antibodies been produced [29,35,40], but recent work has produced a PD-1/CD28 chimeric switch receptor for use in canine B-cell lymphoma [50]. It is also significant that TIM3 is more highly expressed at the mRNA level in many different canine cancer types, relative to PD1 or CTLA4 [28]. Thus, there is an emerging toolbox of antibodies available for use in veterinary canine medicine. Because one of the antibodies we identified (IgG-29 and IgG-26 (data not shown)) can bind to the TIM3 receptor expressed on the surface of living cells (Fig. 10), these antibodies can form a lead TIM3 pathway diagnostic and/or immunotherapeutic for evaluation in canine cancers.

However, the use of such a TIM3 biologic would require careful cell type and patient stratification. Although GAL9 binding inhibition forms one component of how an anti-TIM3 “blocking” immunotherapeutic might operate in some immune cells [51], other clinical issues need to be considered. Data from studies in the murine and human systems provide alternate possibilities. A novel antibody that can inhibit phosphatidylserine binding by TIM3, but not GAL9, promotes receptor internalization [52]. The antibody named Cobolimab targeting TIM3 is now being used in combination with anti-PD-1 antibodies for a subset of patients [53] because current thought is that TIM3 inhibition alone might not have the highest therapeutic efficacy. For example, dual targeting of TIM3 and CD39 [54] provides another example of combined TIM3 therapeutics having a benefit. Thus, emerging research can be focused on developing further pre-clinical and clinical models to test the efficacy of these antibodies in regulating the TIM-3 pathway in veterinary animal cancers. To our knowledge, there are no commercial antibodies to canine TIM3; our current TIM3 antibodies that bind to specific epitopes (Fig. 6) are available upon request for the research community to use and characterize in basic research and clinical settings. Due to the complex nature of TIM3 it is also likely that additional antibodies with distinct epitopes, to the ones we report here, would be needed to fully capture *in vivo* physiological regulation. The use of NGS sequencing of phage libraries provides an approach for cloning rare antibodies with different epitopes for this type of analysis.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jack Brydon: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Radovan Krejcir:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mariana Grima:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Filip Zavadil-Kokas:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zuzana Kuncova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Sousan Sousan:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Robin L. Pflughaupt:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Jennifer R. Thomson:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Paul Davies:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Ella Senior:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Geoffrey A. Wood:** Investigation, Resources. **Kathryn L. Ball:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **David Saliba:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David J. Argyle:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Borivoj Vojtesek:**

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Data statement

All antibody sequencing data, including NGS sequencing reads and scFv antibody sequencing reads, are currently confidential information not for disclosure and the data are available under an MTA.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no declaration of competing interests to disclose.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] D. Hanahan, R.A. Weinberg, Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation, *Cell* 144 (2011) 646–674.
- [2] M.T. Chow, A. Moller, M.J. Smyth, Inflammation and immune surveillance in cancer, *Semin. Cancer Biol.* 22 (2012) 23–32.
- [3] N. Taefeshokh, B. Baradaran, A. Baghbanzadeh, S. Taefeshokh, Promising approaches in cancer immunotherapy, *Immunobiology* 225 (2020) 151875.
- [4] J. Duell, J. Westin, The future of immunotherapy for diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, *Int. J. Cancer* 156 (2025) 251–261.
- [5] R. Baghban, L. Roshangar, R. Jahanban-Esfahlan, K. Seidi, A. Ebrahimi-Kalan, M. Jaymand, S. Kolahian, T. Javaheri, P. Zare, Tumor microenvironment complexity and therapeutic implications at a glance, *Cell Commun. Signal.* 18 (2020) 59.
- [6] J.G. Cyster, C.D.C. Allen, B cell responses: cell interaction dynamics and decisions, *Cell* 177 (2019) 524–540.
- [7] T. van den Broek, J.A.M. Borghans, F. van Wijk, The full spectrum of human naive T cells, *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 18 (2018) 363–373.
- [8] R.D. Mazar, N. Nathan, A. Gilboa, L. Stoler-Barak, L. Moss, I. Solomonov, A. Hanuna, Y. Divinsky, M.D. Shmueli, H. Hezroni, I. Zaretsky, M. Mor, O. Golani, G. Sabah, A. Jakobson-Setton, N. Yanichkin, M. Feinmesser, D. Tsoref, L. Salman, E. Yeoshoua, E. Peretz, I. Erlich, N.M. Cohen, J.M. Gershoni, N. Freund, Y. Merbl, G. Yaari, R. Eitan, I. Sagi, Z. Shulman, Tumor-reactive antibodies evolve from non-binding and autoreactive precursors, *Cell* 185 (2022) 1208–1222 e1221.
- [9] R.E. O'Neill, X. Cao, Co-stimulatory and co-inhibitory pathways in cancer immunotherapy, *Adv. Cancer Res.* 143 (2019) 145–194.
- [10] J.V. Gorman, J.D. Colgan, Regulation of T cell responses by the receptor molecule Tim-3, *Immunol. Res.* 59 (2014) 56–65.
- [11] N. Joller, A.C. Anderson, V.K. Kuchroo, LAG-3, TIM-3, and TIGIT: distinct functions in immune regulation, *Immunity* 57 (2024) 206–222.
- [12] Y. Wolf, A.C. Anderson, V.K. Kuchroo, TIM3 comes of age as an inhibitory receptor, *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 20 (2020) 173–185.
- [13] C.M. Smith, A. Li, N. Krishnamurthy, M.A. Lemmon, Phosphatidylserine binding directly regulates TIM-3 function, *Biochem. J.* 478 (2021) 3331–3349.
- [14] A. Delova, A. Pasc, A. Monari, Interaction of the immune system TIM-3 protein with a model cellular membrane containing phosphatidyl-serine lipids, *Chemistry* 30 (2024) e202304318.

- [15] A. de Mingo Pulido, K. Hanggi, D.P. Celas, A. Gardner, J. Li, B. Batista-Bittencourt, E. Mohamed, J. Trillo-Tinoco, O. Osunmakinde, R. Pena, A. Onimus, T. Kaisho, J. Ruffmann, K. McEachern, H. Soliman, V.C. Luca, P.C. Rodriguez, X. Yu, B. Raffell, The inhibitory receptor TIM-3 limits activation of the cGAS-STING pathway in intra-tumoral dendritic cells by suppressing extracellular DNA uptake, *Immunity* 54 (2021) 1154–1167 e1157.
- [16] Y.H. Huang, C. Zhu, Y. Kondo, A.C. Anderson, A. Gandhi, A. Russell, S.K. Dougan, B.S. Petersen, E. Melum, T. Pertel, K.L. Clayton, M. Raab, Q. Chen, N. Beauchemin, P.J. Yazaki, M. Pyzik, M.A. Ostrowski, J.N. Glickman, C.E. Rudd, H.L. Ploegh, A. Franke, G.A. Petsko, V.K. Kuchroo, R.S. Blumberg, CEACAM1 regulates TIM-3-mediated tolerance and exhaustion, *Nature* 517 (2015) 386–390.
- [17] C. Bailly, X. Thuru, L. Goossens, J.F. Goossens, Soluble TIM-3 as a biomarker of progression and therapeutic response in cancers and other of human diseases, *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 209 (2023) 115445.
- [18] L. Monney, C.A. Sabatos, J.L. Gaglia, A. Ryu, H. Waldner, T. Chernova, S. Manning, E.A. Greenfield, A.J. Coyle, R.A. Sobel, G.J. Freeman, V.K. Kuchroo, Th1-specific cell surface protein Tim-3 regulates macrophage activation and severity of an autoimmune disease, *Nature* 415 (2002) 536–541.
- [19] R.B. Jones, L.C. Ndhlovu, J.D. Barbour, P.M. Sheth, A.R. Jha, B.R. Long, J.C. Wong, M. Satkunarajah, M. Schwenker, J.M. Chapman, G. Gyenes, B. Vali, M.D. Hycrza, F.Y. Yue, C. Kovacs, A. Sassi, M. Loutfy, R. Halpenny, D. Persad, G. Spotts, F. M. Hecht, T.W. Chun, J.M. McCune, R. Kaul, J.M. Rini, D.F. Nixon, M.A. Ostrowski, Tim-3 expression defines a novel population of dysfunctional T cells with highly elevated frequencies in progressive HIV-1 infection, *J. Exp. Med.* 205 (2008) 2763–2779.
- [20] M. Das, C. Zhu, V.K. Kuchroo, Tim-3 and its role in regulating anti-tumor immunity, *Immunol. Rev.* 276 (2017) 97–111.
- [21] Y. Kikushige, T. Shima, S. Takayanagi, S. Urata, T. Miyamoto, H. Iwasaki, K. Takenaka, T. Teshima, T. Tanaka, Y. Inagaki, K. Akashi, TIM-3 is a promising target to selectively kill acute myeloid leukemia stem cells, *Cell Stem Cell* 7 (2010) 708–717.
- [22] W. Du, M. Yang, A. Turner, C. Xu, R.L. Ferris, J. Huang, L.P. Kane, B. Lu, TIM-3 as a target for cancer immunotherapy and mechanisms of action, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 18 (2017).
- [23] Y. Wang, T. Feng, H. Li, Y. Xiong, Y. Tao, Gal-9/Tim-3 signaling pathway activation suppresses the generation of Th17 cells and promotes the induction of Foxp3(+) regulatory T cells in renal ischemia-reperfusion injury, *Mol. Immunol.* 156 (2023) 136–147.
- [24] M. Zhang, C. Liu, Y. Li, H. Li, W. Zhang, J. Liu, L. Wang, C. Sun, Galectin-9 in cancer therapy: from immune checkpoint ligand to promising therapeutic target, *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.* 11 (2023) 1332205.
- [25] S. Kandel, P. Adhikary, G. Li, K. Cheng, The TIM3/Gal9 signaling pathway: an emerging target for cancer immunotherapy, *Cancer Lett.* 510 (2021) 67–78.
- [26] A.K. LeBlanc, C.N. Mazcko, Improving human cancer therapy through the evaluation of pet dogs, *Nat. Rev. Cancer* 20 (2020) 727–742.
- [27] F.F. Gellrich, M. Schmitz, S. Beissert, F. Meier, Anti-PD-1 and novel combinations in the treatment of Melanoma-An update, *J. Clin. Med.* 9 (2020).
- [28] M. Kocikowski, M. Yebenes Mayordomo, J. Alfaro, M. Parys, Barking up the right tree: immune checkpoint signatures of human and dog cancers, *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 21 (2025) e1013270.
- [29] M. Lisowska, E.G. Worrall, F. Zavadil-Kokas, K. Charlton, E. Murray, M.A. Mohtar, R. Krejcir, V. Hrabal, J. Brydon, A.G. Urionabarrenetxea, D.G. Saliba, M. Grima, U. Kalathiya, P. Muller, A. Krejci, B. Vojtesek, K.L. Ball, R. Fahraeus, D.J. Argyle, M. Parys, T.R. Hupp, The development of a canine single-chain phage antibody library to isolate recombinant antibodies for use in translational cancer research, *Cell Rep. Methods* 5 (2025) 101008.
- [30] G. Kemmer, S. Keller, Nonlinear least-squares data fitting in excel spreadsheets, *Nat. Protoc.* 5 (2010) 267–281.
- [31] C.R. Schott, L. Ludwig, A.J. Muetsaers, R.A. Foster, G.A. Wood, The autophagy inhibitor spautin-1, either alone or combined with doxorubicin, decreases cell survival and colony formation in canine appendicular osteosarcoma cells, *PLoS One* 13 (2018) e0206427.
- [32] A.H. Laustsen, V. Greiff, A. Karatt-Vellatt, S. Muyldermans, T.P. Jenkins, Animal immunization, in vitro display technologies, and machine learning for antibody discovery, *Trends Biotechnol.* 39 (2021) 1263–1273.
- [33] L. Burch, H. Shimizu, A. Smith, C. Patterson, T.R. Hupp, Expansion of protein interaction maps by phage peptide display using MDM2 as a prototypical conformationally flexible target protein, *J. Mol. Biol.* 337 (2004) 129–145.
- [34] A.C. Dalton, W.A. Barton, Over-expression of secreted proteins from mammalian cell lines, *Protein Sci.* 23 (2014) 517–525.
- [35] S. Yoshimoto, N. Chester, A. Xiong, E. Radaelli, H. Wang, M. Brillantes, G. Gulendran, P. Glassman, D.L. Siegel, N.J. Mason, Development and pharmacokinetic assessment of a fully canine anti-PD-1 monoclonal antibody for comparative translational research in dogs with spontaneous tumors, *mAbs* 15 (2023) 2287250.
- [36] J. Jumper, R. Evans, A. Pritzel, T. Green, M. Figurnov, O. Ronneberger, K. Tunyasuvunakool, R. Bates, A. Zidek, A. Potapenko, A. Bridgland, C. Meyer, S.A. A. Kohl, A.J. Ballard, A. Cowie, B. Romera-Paredes, S. Nikolov, R. Jain, J. Adler, T. Back, S. Petersen, D. Reiman, E. Clancy, M. Zielinski, M. Steinegger, M. Pacholska, T. Berghammer, S. Bodenstein, D. Silver, O. Vinyals, A.W. Senior, K. Kavukcuoglu, P. Kohli, D. Hassabis, Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold, *Nature* 596 (2021) 583–589.
- [37] M. Mirdita, K. Schütze, Y. Moriwaki, L. Heo, S. Ovchinnikov, M. Steinegger, ColabFold: making protein folding accessible to all, *Nat. Methods* 19 (2022) 679–682.
- [38] S.A. Bobrovnik, Determination of antibody affinity by ELISA. Theory, *J. Biochem. Biophys. Methods* 57 (2003) 213–236.
- [39] L. Heinrich, N. Tissot, D.J. Hartmann, R. Cohen, Comparison of the results obtained by ELISA and surface plasmon resonance for the determination of antibody affinity, *J. Immunol. Methods* 352 (2010) 13–22.
- [40] M. Igase, Y. Nemoto, K. Itamoto, K. Tani, M. Nakaichi, M. Sakurai, Y. Sakai, S. Noguchi, M. Kato, T. Tsukui, T. Mizuno, A pilot clinical study of the therapeutic antibody against canine PD-1 for advanced spontaneous cancers in dogs, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (2020) 18311.
- [41] R.A. Keenan, A. De Riva, B. Corleis, L. Hepburn, S. Licence, T.H. Winkler, I. L. Martensson, Censoring of autoreactive B cell development by the pre-B cell receptor, *Science* 321 (2008) 696–699.
- [42] A. Braganza, K. Wallace, L. Pell, C.R. Parrish, D.L. Siegel, N.J. Mason, Generation and validation of canine single chain variable fragment phage display libraries, *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 139 (2011) 27–40.
- [43] B.U. Hur, J.B. Yoon, L.K. Liu, S.H. Cha, Isolation of a human anti-epidermal growth factor receptor fab antibody, EG-19-11, with subnanomolar affinity from naive immunoglobulin repertoires using a hierarchical antibody library system, *Immunol. Lett.* 134 (2010) 55–61.
- [44] S. Jacobs, P. Cuatrecasas, Disulfide reduction converts the insulin receptor of human placenta to a low affinity form, *J. Clin. Invest.* 66 (1980) 1424–1427.
- [45] A.M. Coley, N.V. Campanale, J.L. Casey, A.N. Hodder, P.E. Crewther, R.F. Anders, L.M. Tilley, M. Foley, Rapid and precise epitope mapping of monoclonal antibodies against *Plasmodium falciparum* AMA1 by combined phage display of fragments and random peptides, *Protein Eng.* 14 (2001) 691–698.
- [46] A. Krejci, T.R. Hupp, M. Lexa, B. Vojtesek, P. Muller, Hammock: a hidden Markov model-based peptide clustering algorithm to identify protein-interaction consensus motifs in large datasets, *Bioinformatics* 32 (2016) 9–16.
- [47] S. Ferdous, S. Kelm, T.S. Baker, J. Shi, A.C.R. Martin, B-cell epitopes: discontinuity and conformational analysis, *Mol. Immunol.* 114 (2019) 643–650.
- [48] J.H. Lee, R. Yin, G. Ofek, B.G. Pierce, Structural features of antibody-peptide recognition, *Front. Immunol.* 13 (2022) 910367.
- [49] N.J. Mason, N. Chester, A. Xiong, A. Rotolo, Y. Wu, S. Yoshimoto, P. Glassman, G. Gulendran, D.L. Siegel, Development of a fully canine anti-canine CTLA4 monoclonal antibody for comparative translational research in dogs with spontaneous tumors, *mAbs* 13 (2021) 2004638.
- [50] S. Yoshimoto, A. Kudo, A. Rotolo, K. Foos, L. Olenick, S. Takagi, N.J. Mason, Validation of a PD-1/CD28 chimeric switch receptor to augment CAR-T function in dogs with spontaneous B cell lymphoma, *iScience* 27 (2024) 110863.
- [51] Y. Ju, X. Shang, Z. Liu, J. Zhang, Y. Li, Y. Shen, Y. Liu, C. Liu, B. Liu, L. Xu, Y. Wang, B. Zhang, J. Zou, The Tim-3/galectin-9 pathway involves in the homeostasis of hepatic Tregs in a mouse model of concanavalin A-induced hepatitis, *Mol. Immunol.* 58 (2014) 85–91.
- [52] Z. Kuang, L. Li, P. Zhang, B. Chen, M. Wu, H. Ni, S. Yi, J. Zou, J. Liu, A novel antibody targeting TIM-3 resulting in receptor internalization for cancer immunotherapy, *Antib. Ther.* 3 (2020) 227–236.
- [53] D. Davar, Z. Eroglu, M. Milhem, C. Becerra, M. Gutierrez, A. Ribas, B. Di Pace, T. Wang, H. Zhang, S. Ghosh, N. Yanamandra, T. Borgovan, S. Srivats, A. Waszak, A. Dhar, P. LoRusso, Combined targeting of PD-1 and TIM-3 in patients with locally advanced or metastatic non-small cell lung cancer: AMBER part 2B, *Clin. Cancer Res.* 31 (2025) 3443–3451.
- [54] M. Sade-Feldman, K. Yizhak, S.L. Bjorgaard, J.P. Ray, C.G. de Boer, R.W. Jenkins, D.J. Lieber, J.H. Chen, D.T. Frederick, M. Barzily-Rokni, S.S. Freeman, A. Reuben, P. J. Hoover, A.C. Villani, E. Ivanova, A. Portell, P.H. Lizotte, A.R. Aref, J.P. Eliane, M.R. Hammond, H. Vitzthum, S.M. Blackmon, B. Li, V. Gopalakrishnan, S. M. Reddy, Z.A. Cooper, C.P. Paweletz, D.A. Barbie, A. Stemmer-Rachaminov, K. T. Malherty, J.A. Wargo, G.M. Boland, R.J. Sullivan, G. Getz, N. Hacohen, Defining T cell states associated with response to checkpoint immunotherapy in melanoma, *Cell* 176 (2019) 404.
- [55] K. Lindblad-Toh, C.M. Wade, T.S. Mikkelsen, E.K. Karlsson, D.B. Jaffe, M. Kamal, M. Clamp, J.L. Chang, E.J. Kulbokas 3rd, M.C. Zody, E. Mauceli, X. Xie, M. Breen, R.K. Wayne, E.A. Ostrander, C.P. Ponting, F. Galibert, D.R. Smith, P.J. DeJong, E. Kirkness, P. Alvarez, T. Biagi, V. Brockman, J. Butler, C.W. Chin, A. Cook, J. Cuff, M.J. Daly, D. DeCaprio, S. Gnerre, M. Grabherr, M. Kellis, M. Kleber, C. Bardeleben, L. Goodstadt, A. Heger, C. Hite, L. Kim, K.P. Koepfli, H.G. Parker, J. P. Pollinger, S.M. Searle, N.B. Sutter, R. Thomas, C. Webber, J. Baldwin, A. Abebe, A. Abouelleil, L. Aftuck, M. Ait-Zahra, T. Aldredge, N. Allen, P. An, S. Anderson, C. Antoine, H. Arachchi, A. Aslam, L. Ayotte, P. Bachantsang, A. Barry, T. Bayul, M. Benamara, A. Berlin, D. Bessette, B. Blitshteyn, T. Bloom, J. Blye, L. Boguslavskiy, C. Bonnet, B. Boukhgalter, A. Brown, P. Cahill, N. Calixte, J. Camarata, Y. Cheshatsang, J. Chu, M. Citroen, A. Collymore, P. Cooke, T. Dawoe, R. Daza, K. DeKtor, S. DeGray, N. Dhargay, K. Dooley, K. Dooley, P. Dorje, K. Dorjee, L. Dorris, N. Duffey, A. Dupes, O. Egbiremolen, R. Elong, J. Falk, A. Farina, S. Faro, D. Ferguson, P. Ferreira, S. Fisher, M. FitzGerald, K. Foley, C. Foley, A. Franke, D. Friedrich, D. Gage, M. Garber, G. Gearin, G. Giannoukos, T. Goode, A. Goyette, J. Graham, E. Grandbois, K. Gyaltsen, N. Hafez, D. Hagopian, B. Hagos, J. Hall, C. Healy, R. Hegarty, T. Honan, A. Horn, N. Houde, L. Hughes, L. Hunicutt, M. Husby, B. Jester, C. Jones, A. Kamat, B. Kanga, C. Kells, D. Khazanovich, A.C. Kieu, P. Kisner, M. Kumar, K. Lance, T. Landers, M. Lara, W. Lee, J.P. Leger, N. Lennon, L. Leuper, S. LeVine, J. Liu, X. Liu, Y. Lokyitsang, T. Lokyitsang, A. Lui, J. Macdonald, J. Major, R. Marabella, K. Maru, C. Matthews, S. McDonough, T. Mehta, J. Meldrim, A. Melnikov, L. Meneus, A. Mihalev, T. Mihova, K. Miller, R. Mittelman, V. Mlenga, L. Mulrain, G. Munson, A. Navidi, J. Naylor, T. Nguyen, N. Nguyen, C. Nguyen, T. Nguyen, R. Nicol, N. Norbu, C. Norbu, N. Novod, T. Nyima, P. Olandt, B. O'Neill, K. O'Neill, S. Osman, L. Oyono, C. Patti, D. Perrin, P. Phunkhang, F. Pierre, M. Priest, A. Rachupka, S. Raghuraman,

R. Rameau, V. Ray, C. Raymond, F. Rege, C. Rise, J. Rogers, P. Rogov, J. Sahalie, S. Settipalli, T. Sharpe, T. Shea, M. Sheehan, N. Sherpa, J. Shi, D. Shih, J. Sloan, C. Smith, T. Sparrow, J. Stalker, N. Stange-Thomann, S. Stavropoulos, C. Stone, S. Stone, S. Sykes, P. Tchuinga, P. Tenzing, S. Tesfaye, D. Thoulutsang, Y. Thoulutsang, K. Topham, I. Topping, T. Tsamla, H. Vassiliev, V. Venkataraman,

A. Vo, T. Wangchuk, T. Wangdi, M. Weiland, J. Wilkinson, A. Wilson, S. Yadav, S. Yang, X. Yang, G. Young, Q. Yu, J. Zainoun, L. Zembek, A. Zimmer, E.S. Lander, Genome sequence, comparative analysis and haplotype structure of the domestic dog, *Nature* 438 (2005) 803–819.